

VERIFICATION OF FLEXURAL RIGIDITY OF THICKNESS OPTIMIZED STRUCTURE MADE OF DISCONTINUOUS CFRTP

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have high specific stiffness and strength compared to metallic materials, therefore it has been expected to be applied into automobile in order to reduce the vehicle weight. Especially, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have attracted attention due to its advantageous properties for mass production automobile such as short molding cycle time, energy absorption capacity and design flexibility. Among them, the most attractive advantage of discontinuous CFRTP is an applicability of variable thickness structure which is difficult to be realized by conventional continuous FRP. For structural optimization of discontinuous CFRTP, it is important to consider actual molding condition, and variable thickness structure has advantages from that perspective. So, this paper focuses on molding pressure of thickness optimized structure made of chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT) and verify its flexural rigidity. As a result, the appropriate molding pressure was the same as flat panels and the bending test results showed that the actual molded structure had the theoretical rigidities.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is an excellent material for lightweight vehicles, because of its much less weight with relative high strength compared with traditional metallic materials. The manufacturing technique of CFRP for lightweight vehicles plays an important role in worldwide energy consumption saving and decreasing the CO₂ emission amount [1], so it will be an alternative to the present steel based vehicles manufacturing technique for its environment-friendly application potential in the future.

By now, carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resin (CFRTS), especially CF/epoxy composite, has been developed since a long time ago because of its high strength. However, compared with carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRTP), CFRTS requires much higher costs because of the difficulty in prepreg storage, in-plant recycling and manufacturing by rapid molding technology [2]. Besides, developing CFRTP possesses some important advantages that CFRTS doesn't have. Firstly, the carbon fiber in CFRTP will not delaminated under tensile stress, which occurs in CFRTS and makes it sensitive to stress concentration [3]. So, CFRTP is more suitable for high cycle molding, especially for the complex-shape parts. Secondary, owing to the thermoplastic property, it relatively easier for CFRTP to recycle. Thus the production cost costs and energy needed can be saved significantly, and the waste during production can be recycled well. Therefore, CFRTP is the better choice than CFRTS for mass production of lightweight vehicles.

Among CFRTP, discontinuous CFRTP, e.g., chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT) have high flexibility to form complex shapes such as plates with ribs by one-shot molding because the discontinuous intermediation materials flow during heat molding. On the other hand, when the molded shape has disturbance of the fiber alignment as shown in Figure 1 [4], the mechanical properties are lower than the theoretical values so that it has been reported that there are some gaps between experimental result and FEA [5]. Therefore, for structural optimization of discontinuous CFRTP, it is important to consider actual molding condition, and variable thickness structure has advantages from that perspective. The optimized structures with gradual thickness variation are

expected not to need high pressure to mold and to be less scattered than flat plates with ribs. In addition to that, the potential of weight reduction of the variable thickness plate is estimated at about 16% comparing to the flat plate with the same flexural rigidity [6]. So, in order to put this technique into practical use, this study investigated appropriate molding pressure of variable thickness structure of CTT and compared 3-point bending test result between experiment and theory.

Figure 1: The cross section of ribs in UT-CTT samples of 12mm length tapes molded under 5MPa [4].

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Optimization

This study deals with thickness optimized structure in 3-point bending test. This part explains the methodology of the optimization [6]. To simplify calculation, both ends supported beam is dealt as cantilever beam as illustrated in Figure 2.

Weight of variable thickness structure is expressed by following formula.

$$W = \rho b \int_0^l t(x) dx \quad (1)$$

where ρ is density of material, b is width of structure, l is length of structure and $t(x)$ is thickness distribution of structure. Deformation of edge, δ is expressed by Timoshenko beam theory.

$$\delta = \frac{12P}{Eb} \int_0^l \frac{(l-x)^2}{t(x)^3} dx + \frac{P}{k_T G b} \int_0^l \frac{1}{t(x)} dx \quad (2)$$

where P is load, E is tensile modulus of material, k_T is shape coefficient and G is shear modulus of material. k_T is expressed by poisson ratio, ν [7].

$$k_T = \frac{10(1+\nu)}{12+11\nu} \quad (3)$$

To get $t(x)$ which minimize W while satisfying constant δ , Lagrange function is introduced.

$$F = W + \lambda \delta = \int_0^l \left(\rho b t(x) + \lambda \frac{12P(l-x)^2}{Eb t(x)^3} + \lambda \frac{P}{k_T G b t(x)^3} \right) dx \quad (4)$$

Let f be integrand in Equation (4) such that f satisfy Euler-Lagrange equation, Equation (5). It follows that $t(x)$ is expressed by Equation (6).

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} - \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t'} \right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$t(x) = \left(\frac{-B + \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC}}{2A} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$A = \rho b$$

$$B = -\lambda \frac{P}{Gk_r b}$$

$$C = -\lambda \frac{36P}{Eb} (l-x)^2 \quad (6)$$

Substitution Equation (6) into Equation (2) leads deflection of thickness optimized structure. Equation (7) follows constraint that the deflection is equal to that of flat plate.

$$\frac{4Pl^3}{Ebt_1^3} + \frac{Pl}{Gk_r bt_1} = \frac{12P}{Eb} \int_0^l \frac{(l-x)^2}{t(x)^3} dx + \frac{P}{k_r Gb} \int_0^l \frac{1}{t(x)} dx \quad (7)$$

where t_1 is thickness of flat plate. Then, it was necessary to solve Equation 7 for λ by Newton-Raphson method. Newton-Raphson method is a numerical analysis method for finding successively better approximation to the roots of real-valued function.

In this study, use parameter of CTT shown in table 1 and set convergence rate of Newton-Raphson method 1.0×10^4 , λ is calculated. Substitution of λ into Equation (6) leads $t(x)$ of thickness optimized structure which have the same flexural rigidity as 3mm flat panel. The result is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Target of optimization.

Figure 3: Thickness distribution of optimized structure.

Table 1: Parameter for structural optimization of UT-CTT

P	l	b	t_1	E	G	ν
[N]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[MPa]	[MPa]	
100	48	35	3	41000	1100	0.33

2.2 Specimen design

The thickness optimized shape of 2.1 is not suitable for 3-point bending test. So, this section show how to modify the shape and decide specimen design.

The center of analysis shape is not smooth and this can cause stress concentration. To eliminate this effect, the thickness of the center was set lower than theoretical value and spline curve was drawn. In addition to that, the thickness of the edge is too thin. This part is difficult to make and the test result can scatter more because the number of contained tapes is little. So, minimum thickness is set 1mm in order to make it easier to mold and stabilize flexural rigidity. Therefore, specimen design is decided shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Theoretical shape and modified design.

2.3 Material

The material used in this study was unidirectional CF/PA6 (Polyamide 6) prepreg sheet with the thickness of 44 μ m, and the carbon fiber volume fraction (V_f) is about 55%. Carbon fiber was provided by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd and PA6 was provided by Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc. this sheet was made by using tow spreading technology of Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. These kinds of technologies recently attract attention because of its improvement of some mechanical properties.

In order to cut the sheet to chopped tapes, an automated tape cutter and Tomson cutter were used. The length of the tapes is 18mm and the width is 5mm. The chopped tapes were dispersed by wet dispersion process and the dispersed tapes are briefly heated and compressed to make fixed and portable sheet. This procedure can also prevent tapes from orientating out-of plane direction.

A steel mold with 125 \times 125 mm² was used for compression molding. The intermediate sheets were laminated and placed into this mold (Figure 5). The temperature of the mold was up to 255 $^{\circ}$ C. Molding pressure was first 1MPa and maintained 10 minutes and the pressure was increased up to 5, 7, 10, or 18MPa and maintained 15 minutes. It was cooled down to below around 60 $^{\circ}$ C and CTT plate was removed from the mold (Figure 6).

Figure 5: The stack of intermediate sheets of UT-CTT.

Figure 6: The UT-CTT plate molded under 5MPa (a), 7MPa (b), 10MPa (c), and 18MPa (d)

2.4 Mechanical testing procedure

Six specimens for 3-point bending test were cut from one plate molded under each pressure. The width of specimen is 35 mm and the length is 125 mm. 3-point bending test was performed with stroke speed of 2.0 mm/min and span length of 96mm (Figure 7). Flexural rigidity was calculated from load-deflection curve. Deflection range used for the calculation of flexural rigidity was 1.0 mm with a start point of 0.5 mm and an end point of 1.5 mm. The number of tests was six for each molding pressure.

Figure 7: Schematic diagram of 3-point bending test in this study

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Molding pressure and flexural rigidity

Specimens which were molded under 5, 7, 10, and 18MPa were named CTT_5MPa, CTT_7MPa, CTT_10MPa, and CTT_18MPa.

Figure 8 showed a comparison of Load-deflection curve of each test and flexural rigidity, CoV, and maximum load were shown in Table 2. The flexural rigidity and the strength of CTT_5MPa and CTT_7MPa were higher than CTT_10MPa and CTT_18MPa. It was assumed that high pressure cause some shape defects. In order to examine the flowability more closely, cross section of the specimens was observed by digital microscope (Figure 9). As a result, CTT_18MPa had resin rich area at the thickness changing point. On the other hand, CTT_5MPa was molded without resin rich area, void part, or disturbance of fiber alignment.

CTT_5MPa had more white spots on the surface than CTT_7MPa (Figure 10). This spot seemed air bubble which generated until molding and came to surface during cooling procedure. This air bubble seemed not to influence flexural rigidity and strength because there was not much different in meaning between mechanical properties of CTT_5MPa and CTT_7MPa.

Therefore, the appropriate molding pressure of thickness optimized structure of CTT was 5MPa which is the same as that of flat panel.

Figure 8: Load-deflection curve of CTT_5MPa(a), CTT_7MPa (b), CTT_10MPa (c), and CTT_18MPa (d)

Table 2: Result of 3-point bending test

Molding pressure [MPa]	P/δ [N/mm]	CoV [%]	Maximum load [N]
5	168	5.8	1476
7	169	5.0	1496
10	164	3.9	1418
18	156	6.3	1350

P/δ : flexural rigidity
 CoV: coefficient of variation

Figure 9: Cross section of CTT_5MPa and CTT_18MPa

Figure 10: White spot on the surface of CTT_5MPa

3.2 Comparing experimental result with theory

The flexural rigidity of flat panel of CTT was expressed by flexural modulus, E_b

$$\frac{P}{\delta} = \frac{4E_b b t_1^3}{l^3} \quad (8)$$

E_b of CTT and its scatter could be analyzed by Nakashima's model [8]. Using this model, the flexural rigidity of CTT_5MPa was the same as 2.99mm thickness flat panel. In addition to that, this model shew the CoV of flexural rigidity of 3mm thickness flat panel was 5.99% which was also nearly equal to that of CTT_5MPa.

Thus, thickness optimized structure of CTT which were molded under low pressure had theoretical flexural rigidity and its scatter was the same as flat panel (Figure 11). So, it was assumed that FEA of these structure show good agreement with experimental result unlike plates with rib. It was shown that the structural optimization applying thickness distribution was suited to CTT where simple structure were required.

Figure 11: Flexural rigidity of theory and experimental results

4 CONCLUSION

The results can be concluded as follows:

- (1) The fracture origin of thickness optimized structure was not the center but the thickness changing point because of stress concentration. So, it is necessary to smooth analysis solution of optimization not to cause this.
- (2) Thickness optimized structure of CTT was molded without shape defects under the same pressure as flat plate, 5MPa. Flexural rigidity and strength of the structure which was molded under higher pressure than 10MPa were lower because of resin rich area.
- (3) Actual optimized structure of CTT had theoretical flexural rigidity and the CoV was the same as flat panel. Thus, it was assumed that FEA of this structure show good agreement with experimental result.

Therefore, this study showed the possibility of the structural optimization applying thickness distribution to CTT.

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